

DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH PREDICTION OF IMPACTED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A compliance matching technique is proposed to characterize the impact damage in terms of equivalent crack length. Once the characterization of the impact damage is achieved in terms of equivalent crack length, the strain energy release rate can be calculated directly from the change in the compliance value. The present study uses the critical strain energy release rate, also known as fracture toughness, to predict the residual strength of the impact damaged composites. Through an extensive test program involving a family of laminated composite beam specimens subjected to low velocity impacts and three point bending, the study shows the effectiveness of the concept for predicting the residual strength.

Key words : Damage characterization - Residual strength - Equivalent crack size - Low velocity impacts - Laminated composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites offer several advantages for aircraft structures which require a combination of high strength and stiffness with low weight. However, these composites are prone to defects caused by impacts which may significantly reduce the strength. The defects include fibre breakages, matrix cracks, debonds and delamination. The internal damage caused during impact may not be visible from the surface but can result in a significant reduction in the residual strength. Therefore it is necessary to quantify the internal damage caused during impact to gain a full understanding of the reduction in the residual strength of laminated composites. It is proposed that the change in compliance may be considered as a parameter to reflect the extent of damage in the composite.

Prediction of residual strength of impacted composites has received considerable attention in recent times. An analogy in terms of residual strength was developed between the damage inflicted by a localized single-point hard-particle impact and the damage inflicted by inserting a flaw of known dimensions by Husman et al [1]. Cantwell et al [2] and Caprino [3] studied the residual strength of laminated composites after single impacts at various absorbed energy levels. Wyrick and Adams [4] conducted experiments to predict the residual strength of composite plates subjected to repeated impacts at various energy levels.

Table : 1 Material Properties

E_x	$1.99 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^2$
E_y	$1.99 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^2$
μ_{xy}	0.28
Volume fraction	40%

Figure 1. Experimental impact apparatus

The present study makes use of the equivalent crack concept developed by Gaggar and Broutman [5] based on compliance matching procedure to estimate the size of the equivalent crack of the impacted beam specimens. The method is then extended to predict the residual strength of the laminate. Cross ply woven fibre laminated bend specimens were fabricated and employed for the present work. The three point bending was chosen primarily due to simplicity of the method. Results from the tests conducted are presented and compared with the predicted values.

2. EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1. Specimen selection

The three point bend specimens were fabricated generally according to ASTM STP 381 [6]. Specimens were prepared using isophthalic polyester resin and woven roving fibre glass materials by hand lay-up technique. Square panels of side 320 mm and 8 mm thickness were fabricated. Beam specimens with a cross section of 8 mm by 16 mm were cut using a diamond wheel cutter. ASTM STP 381 recommends values of width to thickness ratio (w/t) of 2.0 and length to width ratio (l/w) greater than 5.0. In order to have considerable flexibility, the span of the beam was kept at 140 mm. Table 1 gives the properties of the test specimens. Straight cracks of different lengths were introduced by saw cuts.

2.2. Impact tests

Impact tests on simply supported composite beams were conducted using a drop weight impact testing machine as shown in Figure 1. Beams with both edgewise and flatwise positions as shown in Figure 2 were subjected to impacts. The impactor which has a nose diameter of

Figure 3. Three point bend test

Figure 2. Beam specimens for impact loading
 a) Edgewise specimen
 b) Flatwise specimen

10 mm can be dropped from different heights. Provisions were made to vary the mass of the impactor. A mass of 4.8 kg was dropped on the simply supported beam specimens from various heights.

2.3. Residual strength tests

Bend tests were performed in the Olsen Universal Testing System as shown in Figure 3. The tests were conducted generally as was done by Guess and Hoover [7]. Failure loads as well as load-displacement data were obtained for all beam specimens subjected to impact loads. Bend tests were also conducted for unflawed specimens and specimens with machined straight cracks. The specimens were mounted in both edgewise and flatwise conditions.

3. BACKGROUND

3.1. Concept of compliance matching process

The compliance matching procedure is based on the assumption that the compliance may be taken as a measure of crack length and, hence, effective crack length in a damaged specimen may be estimated by matching its compliance with the compliance of a specimen having straight machined notch. Load - displacement curves for specimens with various machined notches were obtained as shown in Figure 4 by testing the specimens in a bending environment. Initial compliance obtained from Figure 4 is then plotted against the crack length as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Load Vs Deflection

Figure 5. Compliance Vs Crack length

This curve is referred as the compliance curve or crack length estimation curve. To estimate the equivalent crack length of the impact damaged specimens, the initial compliance of specimens are obtained using static bend tests. The crack lengths against the measured compliance values from Figure 5 are then assumed to be the estimated equivalent crack length of the damaged specimens.

3.2. Theoretical Considerations

Two fracture toughness parameters have been developed from LEFM dealing with the onset of crack initiation and propagation. The toughness can be described either by the stress parameter known as critical stress intensity factor, or by the characteristic energy parameter known as critical strain energy release rate, G_c . The present study makes use of the energy technique to predict the strength of the beam specimen.

The critical strain energy release rate is defined as

$$G_c = - \frac{\partial U}{\partial A} \delta_c \quad \text{----- 1}$$

where U is the strain energy, A is the new fracture surface area and δ_c is the midspan deflections. Equation 1 can also be written in terms of compliance as

$$G_c = - \frac{1}{2B} P_c^2 \times \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad \text{----- 2}$$

where B is the width of the specimen, P_c is the failure load, ∂C is the change in compliance and ∂a is the increase in crack length.

Figure 6. Impact height Vs Compliance for edgewise specimen

Figure 7. Impact height Vs Compliance for flatwise specimen

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Typical compliance ratio-crack size responses of the beam specimens are shown in Figure 5, where C_0 and C_d are the initial compliances of the undamaged and damaged specimen respectively. The curve shows that the progressive decrement in compliance ratio with respect to the incremental crack length. Figures 6 and 7 show the response of edgewise and flatwise beam specimens subjected to heavy impacts where load is dropped from different heights. For the above cases, though the visible crack formation is not seen, a well marked localized damage area, which consists of fibre breakage, matrix cracks, debonding and delaminations, is noticed. These factors cause the system to become more and more compliant, which can be seen from these cases.

Typical results for the variation of G_c with respect to the crack length are shown in Figures 8 and 9. Except for the initial damage progression zone, G_c remains a constant and justifies its use as the parameter to characterize the final damage in impacted composite beams.

In order to realise the aim of this study, a compliance matching process, as explained in section 3.1, is used to estimate the extent of impact damage in terms of equivalent crack lengths. A series of load tests are conducted to assess the estimated equivalent crack length of the impact damaged specimen. Figures 10 and 11 show the residual strength of the damaged specimens plotted against the estimated equivalent crack length, where P_0 and P_d are the failure loads of undamaged and damaged specimens respectively. A comparison has also been made with the strength of the specimens with straight cracks. The results show that the deviation of the predicted values, which are more pronounced at smaller damages, gradually reduces with the increase in the inflicted damage size. This may be attributed to the predominant damage mode of localized matrix cracking during low energy impacts where fibres remain intact to withstand the applied load.

Figure 8. Strain energy release rate Vs crack length for edgewise specimen

Figure 9. Strain energy release rate Vs crack length for flatwise specimen

Figure 10. Residual strength Vs Crack length for edgewise specimen
 ○—○ straight crack
 □—□ estimated equivalent crack

Figure 11. Residual strength Vs Crack length for flatwise specimen
 ○—○ straight crack
 □—□ estimated equivalent crack

5. CONCLUSION AND SIGNIFICANCE

In composite structural analysis an instantaneous crack length is difficult to define or measure. So a method based on the fact that the compliance of the specimen increases with increase in the damage size, has been proposed. The initial compliance values are measured and are transformed into estimated crack length through compliance matching procedure. Cross-ply woven fibre beam specimens are used to study the response when they are subjected to low velocity impacts. Critical strain energy release rates are calculated from the change in compliance and the estimated crack length and are used to predict the residual strength of the specimens.

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